

BOOK CHAPTER WRITING

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Social Media: Sharing Our Lives On The Virtual Platform

Don't use social media to impress people;

Use it to impact people.

— Dave Willis

1. Introduction

2. With exceptional versatility, the information age has slowly but steadily transformed our human life, society, and cultural practices, providing incredible benefits as well as enormous challenges. People are currently at the center of the riotous movement caused by computerization, transformation, creation, and disintermediation, enhancement have flooded and Sci-fi has grown accustomed to science fact. The digital world thrives in everyday cultural activities. It speeds up our thinking process, decision making, and achieving of our objectives & so on. Humans are social organisms; we depend on and even need social connections to balance our lives, emotions, feelings, etc. In this chapter, we have explored what social media is and how it is interrelated to everyday life in relation to digital humanities. How social medicine affects our daily lives. How does the Covid-19 case compel us to change our cultural practices.

3.

4. According to Scott Kirsch “technology is the engine of social change.” Almost every minute, our activity is related to technology. We can't imagine our lives without technology. Among those technologies, social media is one of the best and most vibrant technologies. Nowadays social media technology has become an integral part of our life. It has also intensified our interconnectedness to one another, bringing people from all over the world together digitally. People of all ages use social media, and business organizations use them as a platform for advertising their content. The majority of social media users are content creators. The digital identity contains intangible events or states. Social media channels continue a long tradition of interactive media that reflect the current culture of the time (Oh, 2018). Incredible success Social media is often related to a human psychological need for social incentives, depicting the virtual universe as a Closed Box for modern people. We are influenced by social media in our daily lives. Researchers have talked about how they use social networking sites to establish an interpersonal connection.

5. What makes social media so popular?

Social networking presents people with a plethora of benefits. Some of the major benefits are: social networking sites allow users to meet introduce new people and make friends from all over the world; it enables users to access communities of people who agree with their views and beliefs; They are free to use and simple to implement; highly specialized forums or websites have a vast network of people that can help you find a new career; Platforms such as Twitter have been an important source of real-time news

6. Brief Overview of Social Media

The term "Social Media" was coined in the early 1990s as a positive term for marketing goods that meet the needs of a company's operations within its participants The virtual media, places where they could be entertained, interacted with, and participated in a social setting.” (Bercovici, 2010). As time goes on the term social media is transformed as the technological perspective of communication among peoples are evolved and peoples are connected to the digital platform.

Social media is a platform where people introduce themselves to the globe, sharing individual information and experiences in their daily activities. Social media includes a vast variety of platforms and applications such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat, Reddit, LinkedIn, Trello, Twitch, and many more. People can not only share their thoughts on textual content but also share images, photographs, audio, videos, and so on. The most recent enhancement to this futuristic category is known as "virtual worlds," which are computer-based digital environments created by 3D avatars.

I. Growth of social Networks

Before using any technology or application, it is important to understand its ground concept and operations. Very first impression, Social Media appears to be a novelty, non-obviousness, and usefulness. Historical view allows us to look back to the roots of Social Media. There is continuing discussion about whether an email should be classified as a form of social networking sites or not. Email is also not classified as a social networking platform because it serves as a “Distribution Mechanism” rather than a “Collective Mechanism” (Sajithra, 2013). Ray Tomlinson pioneered web-based email in late 1971. After that Usenet was invented in 1979 by Tom Truscott and Jim Ellis and

it's a globally interconnected Internet discussion framework. In the mid-1970s, Bulletin board systems were one of the earliest examples of social networking. It enabled people to sign in and communicate with each other. IRC (Internet Relay Chat) was first launched to enhance the experience in 1988 and is used for connection and document sharing. The digital diary gave birth to the concept of blogging. Justin Hall, who started private blogging in 1994, is widely regarded as one of the first bloggers. Blogging achieved more popularity during 1999. Sixdegrees was one of the first social networking sites, having been founded in 1997 and it also had approximately a million supporters. Unsurprisingly, SixDegrees was discontinued in 2001. Users could build individual or technical accounts, as well as add friends. That was the early stage of social media.

Figure 1: Social Media History (<https://www.future-marketing.co.uk/the-history-of-social-media>)

In the twenty-first century, social media has opened new horizons and constantly added new things. Friendster was the first comprehensive and genuine social networking website. It was established in 2002 and had over 100 million authorized users; the majority of users were from Asia. This site allowed users to make new friends and expand their current networks. LinkedIn, which was created in 2003, was to use established networks for industry. Earlier, it enabled sharing and interaction through private networking. But now LinkedIn offers new possibilities to build groups, new profile functionality, forums, images, video, and network, and so on. Hi5, was another social media platform that launched in 2003 (Allen, 2016). Currently, it has over one million registered members. Users might choose whether they had to be seen by users in particular or through their device. It was popular in Africa, Asia, and Latin America.

With the advancement of web 2.0 and user-generated content, the definition of social media has been changed dramatically. Web 2.0 is commonly known as a web application that allows user seamless interaction, knowledge sharing, interoperability, interconnectivity, user-centered design, and interaction to www. Web 2.0 sites allow their users to connect or communicate with one another through social media. Social networking grew in prominence after the advent of blogging.

Facebook came into the picture in 2004, released within Harvard University. Since 2004, MySpace has played a vital part in the social media landscape. Facebook surpassed MySpace as the world's biggest social networking site in 2006. YouTube was launched in 2005 and is now one of the most popular video-sharing and video hosting websites. Users can publish their videos to other websites also. By 2006, Tweeter was introduced and it was developed with the intent of serving as a mobile SMS site. And since, it belongs to more than 300 million active users monthly worldwide.

Since 2008, Facebook became open to the general public and quickly gained popularity. It enables users to publish content information such as image, video, audio, text and also customize their pages. Its success grows as a result of its constant upgrading of features. It is very easy to use and offers a private messaging system. Now it allows marketers to reach out to their target audiences through advertisements.

Whatsapp was founded in 2009 (Kaplan, 2010) as a one-to-one messaging service. It has features such as location sharing, voice recording, voice call, video call, status, and so on that are continuously updated. Whatsapp was purchased by Facebook in 2014 for 16 billion dollars.

Instagram was founded in 2010 to connect people all over the world through photo sharing and social interaction. It also enables users to post videos with their Insta wall. There are a plethora of other social networking sites and most of them offer similar features. This chapter does not include all social networking sites.

7. A brief summary of global social media users around the world

Social media networks have evolved into a worldwide movement with tremendous social and economic implications. According to a Statista report, Facebook has over 2.7 billion active users in 2021, making it the world's biggest social network. As a result, both clinicians and academics become interested in online social networks. According to Statista 2021, India has over 290 million Facebook users, making it the top nation in terms of Facebook audience size.

According to Alexa (2021), YouTube is the world's second most popular visited website, subsequently 5th position hold on Facebook, 14th Instagram, and so on. YouTube is often regarded as an important platform for discussing participatory culture. YouTube provides vast content almost every area such as Business, Education, Culture, and Entertainment, etc.

Social networking, which began as a medium of entertainment and communication, is now transforming the most recent marketing technique due to its enormous benefits in the business world. Social networking is used because it has numerous benefits in terms of time, audience, relationships, and expense.

Figure 2: Number of FB user based on country (Millions)

www.statista.com/statistics

8. Five Points about using social media

i. Choose carefully

There are numerous social media sites. Almost every day, a new social media site enters the scene. If you want to use them not only for entertainment purposes but also for business purposes, you must exercise extreme vigilance when determining which one is appropriate for you. You must be always involved. To choose the best platform for a particular reason is determined by the audience to be targeted and the meaning to be conveyed. For example, if you want to reach out to people who like photos or short videos, Instagram is a good place to start.

ii. Pick the application

You familiarise yourself with which social media site you are using. The next move is to decide whether you want to buy it or use it for free. In some cases, most people use Facebook in certain ways for its popularity. If you live in Russia and want to display content in Russian, then VK Note is the best forum for you. Instead of straight ads and selling, it's all about engagement, networking, and interaction. Another example is Japanese Fujifilm, which introduced its social network to create a group for photography lovers.

iii. Ensure activity alignment

In addition, to accomplish the maximum possible reach, you can choose to focus on several Social Media platforms or a collection of different applications within the same community. In this situation, it is important to verify that all of your Social Media accounts are in sync or not. One notable example is Dell's "Digital Nomads" (Kaplan, 2010) programme. "Digital Nomads" merged Facebook and LinkedIn social networking platforms for selling their material, as well as uploading videos on the YouTube channel to highlight the functionality and variety of computers, tablets, and notebooks for end users.

iv. Media plan integration

What applies to various forms of Social Networks often applies to the interaction between Social Networks and conventional networks; although these areas are entirely different, convergence is a crucial aspect. Coca-Cola produced a brief 2-minute short video for its target demographic in 2006, and the video became a huge success on YouTube. Then they use it in mass media platforms for advertising such as TV. In addition to the advantages of high intensity/low-cost media marketing, the campaign also succeeded in noticeable revenue growth.

v. Access for all

It is essential to ensure that all requirements have access to the relevant social media. Although this is definitely a factor, that staff would have unique authorization to view the business blog. Simultaneously, there is a need to minimize the likelihood of the whole company going to devote all of its attention to creating amusing videos and posting them to YouTube.

9. Five points to being social

Andreas M. Kaplan, and Michael Haenlein have discussed details about the social media platform and what does the term "social" entails, and how do we practice it? ([Kaplan, 2010](#)).

A. Be Dynamic

If you'd like to build a friendship with somebody else, you should always take the initiative process to be involved. Social media is mostly about communicating and interacting, so make sure your post is always interesting and engaging with your peers. When assessing your Social Media activities, keep in mind that your company's presence must go beyond reacting to critical feedback. Respondents of Social Media technologies want to fully participate and become both creators and recipients of information, it is known as “prosumers” ([Toffler, 1980](#)).

B. Be interesting

No one wants to talk to a boring man. If you want to engage the recipient with you, you must provide them with a reason for doing so. The first move would be to pay attention to your recipients. Figure out what they want to listen to, what they want to speak about, and what they could find usable, entertaining, or interesting. Then, create and distribute information according to the expectations. Always make an effort to post relevant news with a specific focus ([Sheldon P. A., 2020](#)). Another method is to tell motivational and entertaining stories. The next way to post something scandalous or shocking. Another way to use social networking sites to motivate and encourage people around you. And you don't just need a story; you really need to develop your storytelling abilities.

C. Be humble

Never forget that who spent innumerable hours, on Facebook, Instagram or YouTube know more about this platform and how to use the social media application than you. Before using any application you need to spend some time to discover it and read about its development and its fundamental principles. Essential aspects of among all social media, including blogs, are engagement and feedback. Being positive does not mean thinking less, just thinking of yourself less. A beautiful soul is a joyful soul. Accepting our flaws is beneficial and it is when God's strength is perfected.

D. Be unprofessional

Social Media users are people like you ([Kaplan, 2010](#)), who understand that things well, will not go nicely everytime. So if you're good to with your friend, they might

also offer you free tips on how to improve it for the next time. For an example, if you are ill or have a serious personal problem, it's better for you do not share openly visible photos or status updates. It's better for you to avoid not to upload any professional content.

E. Be honest

Finally, be sincere and obey the social networking site's guidelines. It is easy to tell a lie, but it is hard to maintain track. It is your responsibility to provide accurate facts to your viewers and not lead them astray. But nowadays social media is violating information, they produce misinformation, fake news that is unhealthy for our society. If you're true to what you do, people can trust and rely on you, to be honest. And the more straightforward you are, the easier it would be to support you. Dishonesty causes a lot of misunderstanding and misinterpretation, which can be cleared up by being truthful.

10. Sharing Space

Social Networking technology promotes the ongoing globalization of space –the domain of autonomy and uniformity. On the other side, this technology also formed and encouraged a local scale that is not generally produced but also fragmented.

I. Social Space

Space and spatial practices are regularly used as constructed space, such as field, area, district, locus, or territory but they have various connotations. Space can't exist without the absence of time. Space is not limited to map or pictures. Images are not expressed in a coordinate structure or a unit of measurement, but rather a qualitative value.

Henri Lefebvre (Lefebvre, 1991) offers space philosophy which associated with physical, mental and social aspects. He also argued that space is respectively a *spatial practice* (abstracted concept or perceived space), *representation of space* (a cognitive construct or conceived) and *spaces of representation* (lived sociocultural relationship or local form of knowledge). He defines *abstract* and *social space*. *Abstract* space is the convergence with knowledge and strength. An *abstract space* is like an empty box in which life, culture and society are placed. It is the structured space that is perfect for the individuals who want to regulate society, such as politicians, economists and

organizers. In comparison, *social space* emerges the processes of externalize and materialize daily life through the acts & behaviours of all members of society, including the rulers. The space is created through the interaction of different people over different times. Every society can create its own space, but it is not a socialized space, rather it transcends imaginable borders. The relationship between space and production lies in the constructive view of reality. The human world is socially organized through the constructive elements of dimension (material, symbolic).

II. Social Digital Space

Digital Space is a space that dwelling with ongoing human relationships is becoming profoundly relevant in our everyday activities. There are three crucial factors, according to James Paul Gee (Gee, 2005), first and foremost thing, space requires information or content-- a space-related consideration. It is a form of intellectual interpretation, opinion, or social interaction. Various types of materials, such as video, audio, text, etc. are taken place. As a result, we cannot concern ourselves with philosophical interpretation in the absence of content. A Generator is required to generate each space. The information for space is produced by generators. A generator can be a person, individual, student, teacher etc. Space also requires a portal through which people can access the content. For example, the Instagram app serves as a virtual gateway through which users can access information. Different social media website provides a different user interface for accessing the information.

Online Virtual social space isn't neutral. It dwells in social class conflicts, politics, and inequalities. The simulated space has distinct perceptions, interactions, and memories, which vary based on the programming language. Whereas tangible spaces are collectively built, created, mediated, and developed, negotiated, virtual social spaces are more customizable and easy to control, although we can forcibly model these spaces, such as Google Classroom. The digital space (Calder, 2021) is often considered for designing, producing, replicating, packaging, recording, discarding, modifying, distributing, publicizing, refining, and utilizing information archives. As a result, the similar applications Google Classroom, Zoom, and Microsoft Team have created interactive spaces that are simulated.

Example of Digital Social Space

Recently Covid-19 pandemic has been collapsed almost every education system from primary to higher levels. We have a lot of difficulties. We are gradually moving to the digital social platform for continuing our education. Google Classroom is a prominent example. It is a protected social platform based on a community or group of people where students and teachers can interact with each other. Despite their suffering this Covid-19 situation, every Indian parent wishes to purchase a smartphone in order to provide their children with a better education. We may now argue that social media is beneficial to the educational sector.

11. Human Behaviour and Social Media

a. Social Media Addiction

Addiction to social networks is a similar type of gaming addiction. Earlier studies discovered that social media engagement would promote the production of intense behaviours, resulting in higher levels of dependency (Turel, 2012). According to Mediakix, Addiction to social media is an increasing problem all over the world. The average American invests almost 2 hours per day on social media that calculates to a lifespan of 5 years and four months. Several symptoms are associated with social media addiction: ignorance, mood swing, tolerance, depression, fear, intrapersonal stress, silence, relapse, and so forth (Sheldon, 2019). The previous study has found that for certain individuals, social media is a place to avoid reality and pressure. If we consider Facebook, the funny and entertainment videos attract most of us. Addictions are exacerbated by the content of social networking platforms. Sheldon and Sykes (Sheldon P. A., 2020) investigated how daily routine indicators and personality characteristics could be used to predict YouTube, Twitter, and Facebook addiction. They mentioned that Snapchat caused 20.5% of addiction, Facebook caused 16.6% of addiction, and Instagram caused 12.6% of addiction. Social networking sites have become a safe place for individuals with poor self-esteem. People with greater narcissism rate are even more dependent on social media. People who are prone to ego-enhancing practices may find social media applications are more appealing. The researcher suggested several strategies for young adults and adolescents to overcome this situation. The following are some of the ideas suggested by the researcher: educational consciousness; volunteering activities; restrictions and limitations. To minimize the harmful impacts

of mobile gadgets, it is a smart idea to sign them off two or three hours before going to bed.

- Once a person starts using the application, he/she is tied in a never-ending loop where the person keeps on scroll mindlessly.
- As a result, the person starts spending time in isolation and is cut off from the rest of the world. In fact, they start treating their virtual world as their natural world. It can thus lead to several health problems like depression, obesity etc.
- Teenagers are generally seen as more addicted to social media. They often tend to lose some of their most crucial time, which they could have used to develop personally and professionally.

b. Stress and Anxiety

Stress is described as a sequence of activities involving a provocation that causes a mental reaction. According to Researchers ([Stevens, 2011](#)) one of the reasons undergraduate students used Facebook to relieve tension. Social media friends were linked to higher perceived social reinforcement that was then linked to poor anxiety.

Anxiety disorders are the second most common form of disability across mental disorders. The plurality of anxiety disorders have increased in early adulthood. Researchers discovered that delaying answers to Facebook friend requests is caused by anxiety. According to Labrague ([Labrague, 2014](#)), Facebook may enhance the probability of encountering nasty posts, explicit updates, and abusive comments from Facebook friends, which may promote the formation of these mental states.

c. Depression

Depression is a common disorder characterized by the following symptoms: a depressive mood, a lack of energy and pleasure, excessive tiredness, and a loss of hope, which affect the human intellect. Some imperial researches revealed that a significant amount of time spend on the online conversation can alleviate depressive symptoms. The plurality of analysts have reported that the quantity of social media use is less significant than the manner in which it is used. According to the social contrast principle, we compare ourselves to people who like us or greater than us. Some functions of SNSs, including status alerts and passive usage, can promote rumination.

For example – Assume someone posts an image on Facebook or Instagram, and the image is particularly repulsive, but no one is involved in providing input on these specific posts. The people then lost faith and became depressed.

d. Suicide Rates

Suicide rates among teenagers and young generations have risen dramatically in the last 20 years (Sheldon P. P., 2019). Suicide rates increased in the United States because of stress caused by social media. A study reveals that between 2010 and 2016 the suicide average for American youths in grades 8 to 12 has significantly increased. This may occur for a number of reasons. Social media will make it easier to obtain detailed research about suicide methods. According to Twenge et.al research (Twenge, 2017), 8 % of teenagers who devote 5 hours a day on a digital gadget have at least one suicide attempted, in contrast to 33% of teenagers who invested 2 hours a day on digital equipments. Mental disorder, which is the leading cause of suicide, a very taboo topic in the media. According to the concept, the media may show suicide news acceptable, particularly when influenced by someone's celebrity status.

e. Sleeping Patterns

College students often lament a sleep deprivation in terms of both consistency and time. This may have an effect on daily life by causing low academic success, uncertainty, and a reduction in intellectual ability etc. Studies on the influence of social networking sites on sleep showed negative effects, especially among teenagers. Technology influences sleep efficiency in two phases: light intensity, information or content, and timing. Our sleep pattern is influenced by light emission (Sheldon P. R., 2019). The bright light released electrons, which caused our eyes to strain. People who checked their social media in a short span of time had increased to have a sleep problem. Engaging in stimulating activities before bedtime can disrupt one's ability to sleep. Children also mentioned health problems, a number of eye diseases, eating problems, headaches, and weakness, depression, heart problems, skin problems, nerve problem. In some cases, students encounter these problems after just 30 minutes of using social media and internet.

f. Fitness, Health and Eating Habits

A new research looked at whether people who spent a lot of time on social media were more likely to have an eating disorder. This is not observed to increase that almost all social media sites place a heavy focus on visuals. Syed Abdul et.al (Syed-Abdul, 2013) studies more than 140 YouTube videos. Three physicians checked and graded these videos as insightful, useful, pro-anorexic, etc. The results show that YouTube clips disseminate pro-anorexia-related content. The material of pro-anorexia and its viewers would be heavily promoted. The research also found a low degree of multiple physical activities of college students who mainly used social networks. Social media may trigger tiredness and problems with your eye. Relationship may also damage. The phenomenon with excessive use of social media is referred to as social media addictions.

12. The Good, the Bad and the Ugly side of the Social Media

Positive Impacts of Social Media

1. Social Media and Politics

- Social Media allows people to connect freely. It allows easy communication between two groups which is often considered influential in forming social organisations among the minority/marginalised group.
- Also, in the current tech-savvy world, it is seen that most people get their political information from the use of social media. The influence of social media on political campaigns is tremendous. It has seen a massive increase in the number of people deciding whom to vote based on the information they get from social media.
- For example- Donald Trump's victory in the US and the Narendra Modi in India elections is often seen as a result of good social media management by both parties.

2. Social Media on Society

- In today's world, almost everyone has a mobile phone. A smartphone and internet connection gives a person an opportunity to raise their world. This opportunity is equally available to the people of the marginalised community as well. It gives them a

chance to tell the world the oppression they have faced by just posting about it on any social media platform.

- Social Media thus helps in creating visibility about the issues that persist in society. Without using social media, many of the social, political and environmental ills would have gone unnoticed.
- People can tell their story by writing articles, posting pictures, creating memes etc., by breaking into the mainstream world.

3. Social Media and Commerce

- Organisations highly leverage social media to reach out to their customers and prospective clients. They use social media to market their product, create targeted offerings, generate insights based on it, and stimulate demand. Thus, social media is of great importance in the traditional brick-and-mortar business and e-commerce.
- Insights from various social media are used to give the user recommendations based on his/her prior search results. This is also considered an effective way which is used by a lot of businesses today.
- Social Media is undoubtedly helpful for small business around the world. It allows them to reach out to a more significant number of audiences easily. One of the primary reasons that most organisations are going digital or have started to use a platform-based model is to use social media to its most actual potential.

4. Nurtures Relationships

- The use of social media has expanded relationships and nurtured human emotions. It has helped to improve communication, thus strengthening the bond that the people share.
- It allows one to transcend the boundaries and build relationships irrespective of geographical locations. It binds everyone together.
- With the use of smartphones and an internet connection, it has never been easier to make friends. It brings all people together in the moments that matter.
- Various social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram and Twitter allow to build virtual friends, network with them and share information.

5. Fosters Empathy

- Social media are used as sites where people can share their experiences and ups and downs.
- If a user posts something, it will be viewed by multiple people. So, if someone has gone through a similar situation, he/she can quickly help you come out of a problem.
- It has increased communication, thus making it possible to empathise with the other person virtually. Therefore, social media can also be seen as sites for informal therapy.
- Thus, social media can provide one with instant support and solidarity in times of difficulty.

6. Finds common ground

- Social media has made us realise that the world is a small place. It has allowed like-minded people to come together and network with each other.
- It builds a global community of people with shared interests and goals and allows them to share ideas, views and even collaborate on various projects.
- Sites like Facebook ask about a user's likes and dislikes at the very beginning to filter out content and present it to the user. Social media are used as sites where people can share their experiences and ups and downs.

13. Negative Impacts of Social Media

1. Cyberbullying

- With the advancement in technology and the rise of social media, cyberbullying is one of the major concerns faced by today's generation. It is a type of bullying which happens virtually over any of the social media platforms.
- Facebook is considered one of the powerful cyberbullying platforms.
- It can occur by posting embarrassing or inappropriate photos of someone on social media or trolling a person virtually or sending threats or hurtful messages.

- People can misuse social media to spread misinformation or rumours about someone, which tarnishes a person's reputation.

2. Lack of Privacy

- As we upload something on social media, we are sharing our details with strangers on the internet. A user is giving a sneak-peak to others in his/her life.
- People can misuse social media to spread misinformation or rumours about someone, which tarnishes a person's reputation.
- Since we are a part of the digital work, data loss can have severe implications if not taken seriously. The use of social media also means that it is a compromise with privacy.
- Identity theft, misuse of information and stalking are significant concerns that pop up due to privacy breach on social media sites. Thus, it becomes essential to have a clear distinction between the public and private profile.

3. Negative Feedback

- Social media is an open platform where everyone has access to social sharing. While on the one hand, it is seen as a powerful marketing tool for businesses. On the other hand, it also has the disadvantage of receiving negative feedback from the customers.
- Today influencers have a lot of followers on social media site. Excess negative feedback can further be amplified by them, thus ruining a brand's reputation.
- Social media is a place for instant gratification as well as feedback. Suppose a person does not like a product that you are selling online/ or your write up on a blog/ or a painting that you have posted on Instagram. In that case, people tend to instantly give feedback (primarily negative) without realising the hard work that must have gotten while building the same.

4. Hacking

- Hacking is an illegal practice that has become very common in the digital world. It gives the hacker access to the restricted, personal and valuable information of other people.
- They often steal the person's personal information and then blackmail him/her by posting personal stuff (like photographs, private text messages, bank account details, etc.) on social media, thus making it public.
- Hacking can also include sending spam messages to strangers. If a social media account is hacked, this problem often can't be solved quickly.
- Suppose the business social account of an organisation is hacked. It is not just a problem for the organisation but also the customers as personal and valuable personal information can be leaked.

5. Spread of Fake News

- The use of social media means a person can get in touch with many audiences quickly. With the advancement in technology and better internet facilities, information can easily reach the masses, and so can the misinformation!
- Social media is often used to spread fake news by circulating messages, posting misleading photographs or even sharing inappropriate and out of context videos on social media platforms.
- Generally, the content posted on a virtual platform is not verified, so any person can post anything (correct or incorrect) and spread it to all-world.
- The spread of fake news can have severe implications such as hatred towards a particular community, mob lynching etc.
- WhatsApp and Facebook are often seen as the most common platform to spread misinformation as it is easy to access and is used by most people worldwide.

14. Case Study I

Role of Social Media in Social Movements: #MeToo Movement

With the advancement in technology, the involvement of users on social media has changed. Digital movements have reduced the individual cost of participation, increased accessibility while creating a solid connection between all the users. Compared to offline campaigns, where there is less participation and participants are generally more passive, online activities show increased participation in a self-organised manner.

Social Media platforms have been of great importance to various social movements. And one such social activity is the #MeToo Movement. It reached a large number of audiences with the use of the hashtag on various social media sites. It was used to gain attention on the social issue of sexual harassment that women face.

How did the movement start?

- This movement started in October 2017, where several women came forward on social media platforms using the hashtag to share their incidents of sexual harassment.
- The hashtag was first used in actress Alyssa Milano's tweet, where she wrote that if anyone has ever been sexually assaulted, they should reply with 'me too' to the tweet.
- With the help of this movement, several women came up to tell their stories and horrors of how they have faced gender discrimination at homes, workspaces or any other location.

How was Twitter helpful in the #MeToo Movement?

- This movement spread with the use of social media platform- Twitter.
- Twitter allows real-time sharing of information with many people, where people can engage, talk and do discussions on various topics.
- Any movement, be it offline or online, breaks down to individual actions of the participants.
- Twitter supported communities and victims by relevant hashtags and photos and sharing news; this encouraged others to develop their stories

How impactful was the #MeToo Movement?

- #MeToo Movement was seen as a form of social activism that helped a lot of women.
- It is a movement that went from online to offline and then into the physical world.
- Several influential celebrities, politicians and renowned people's name came through this initiative. It led to know that how they have committed sexual assault on several women.
- Through this movement, the magnitude of sexual abuse was understood by the masses when women in large numbers came together. This movement can be considered as a movement for empowerment with empathy.

Figure 3: Picture showing the tweet by actress Alyssa Milano which started the #MeToo Movement, (Source: www.twitter.com/alyssa_milano)

- It made a public campaign which helped to create an engaging dialogue among the society. It made the public discuss issues that are related to gender equality and sexual misconduct.
- Through this movement, several incidents of sexual misconduct came against Harvey Weinstein, an award-winning film producer.
- Through this movement, several women worldwide came together to share how they have faced sexual abuse and harassment for so long.

- These accusations led many women to use the #MeToo movement to share their experiences of rape and assault.
- Social Media platforms like Twitter and Facebook helped to amplify the #MeToo movement.

15. Case Study II

Spread of Fake News through Social Media from an Indian Perspective

Social media platforms can help to reach the masses and spread a piece of information quickly. However, the same social media sites are also used to spread misinformation and fake news. This spread of false information can have profound implications. Social media algorithms and search engines are manipulated to reach their target audience and mislead them with incorrect information.

Fake news has existed for a long time, from the era of the printing press. However, with the digitisation and coming up of various social media platforms, this has taken a severe turn. Forged videos, edited photos, morphed pictures, use of bots etc., are some of the most common forms which are used to spread fake news.

Social media platforms provide a user with unlimited freedom to post anything they want on the social media platform. As a result, there are higher chances of misuse of information and, hence, fake news.

One of the primary reasons for the spread of fake news is that any information can be posted online without any verification. There is a blurring of boundaries between real and fake news. Further, features such as shares and clicks can lead to its amplification among the masses. Fake news has a shorter life span but a long time and severe consequences like pranks, murders and killings.

Fake news is considered a global issue affecting a large number of people. In India, there has been an increase in the total number of social media users and an increase in the spread of fake news. There is a strong interrelation between the events that happen, the fake news that spreads thereafter, which further instigates the crowd leading to consequences like mob lynching, killing, murders, exclusion from community etc. There are more than 200 million active WhatsApp users in India, and this social media platform is considered one of the primary sources of spreading fake news.

Fake Video circulated on WhatsApp and Facebook triggered the Muzaffarnagar riots of 2013

- Muzaffarnagar riots of 2013 is an example of how social media can trigger mob lynching and cause mass killing. The riots were fuelled by a most likely shot in a tribal area of Pakistan. 2 years the Video was shared on social media platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp and was circulated amongst the masses. However, it was misrepresented to fuel violence.
- It was falsely reported that the Video was shot on August 27 in Kaval village of Muzaffarnagar. The fight was said to be among the two-community youth residing in that area belong to the Muslim and Hindu community. According to it, a young Hindu boy (minority group) was brutally murdered by the Muslim majority group.
- This fake video clip worsened the riots in Muzaffarnagar. As a consequence of it, the violence was followed by mass killing and murder of people. Around 40,000 people, mainly Muslims, were forced to flee from their homes and move to other locations to be safe.

- It was only later that the truth came out that the video was fake and was there on the internet for the past two years. This fake Video was politically engineered. It was done to create riots and polarise voters for the following general assembly elections

Figure 4: A picture showing the riots in Muzaffarnagar that were triggered by circulation of fake video,

(Source: www.zeenews.india.com)

Muzaffarnagar riots of 2013 thus clearly indicate the misuse of social media. It showed us that how social media platforms can be used to mislead people for personal interests. And as a consequence of this, it can lead to loss of life of people.

Fake news is thus fabricated and altered information circulated amongst the masses, which is falsely put and can have profound implications. This unverified information can cause riots. With the advent of technology and improved internet conditions, the spread of fake news is rising more than ever. Thus, there is a need for stricter laws and policies that concern the space of false information.

16. Social Media and COVID-19 pandemic

A COVID-19 pandemic is an unprecedented event of the current times. In these testing situations, social media is used to make more resilient communities. Each coin has two sides: during this pandemic, social media is seen as both a social ally and a potential threat. While social media is being used to connect with friends and families, it has also led to quickly spreading false information.

Figure 5: Graph showing social activity (like, post, share etc) on each of the social media platforms

(Source: www.nature.com/articles)

Figure 6: Pie Chart showing the post discussed topic about COVID-19 pandemic on social media

(Source: www.nature.com/articles)

➤ Dissemination of important information

- Since the pandemic began, social media platforms have been widely used for the rapid dissemination of educational content.

- The infographic about airway management of patients who might be COVID-19 positive was first shared on social media platforms such as Twitter and WeChat.
- Patients and their relatives have actively used Twitter and Instagram to connect with plasma donors across their location. It is also being used to get to know the availability of oxygen cylinder and beds in hospitals.
- Several COVID-19 guidelines by the government regarding lockdowns, curfews, sanitisation etc., are being shared on social media platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook to reach a large number of audiences easily.

➤ **Virtual Education**

- With the COVID-19 pandemic, everything has gone virtual, and so has education.
- This pandemic with physical distance and social isolation could have hampered the education of all the students around the globe. However, most schools today have turned to online mode of instruction.
- This has led to a rise in the number of e-learning platforms that have facilitated remote education.
- With the use of social media platforms like Google Classroom and Microsoft Teams, they have enabled the possibility of students being educated while they are still at their homes.
- Thus, online education is not just seen as an option but a necessity. Even in the post-COVID-19 era, the hybrid education model (both online and offline) is sure to exist.

➤ **Work from Home**

- During the COVID-19 pandemic, a lot of things came to a standstill. It became difficult for business organisations to keep on running. Thus, work from home became the new normal.
- Social media has helped employees do their office work at home and be safe from being infected, which has helped them practice social distancing without facing any difficulty.

- Social Media platforms like Zoom and Google Meet have helped to facilitate work from home. It has helped employees to connect with one another and do their job even when they are unable to meet together in this pandemic.

➤ **Spread of Fake News**

- While on the one hand, social media has been beneficial in this pandemic in the dissemination of information, facilitating online classes and setting up work from home for employees.
- On the other hand, social media has also led to misinformation during this pandemic.
- A lot of fake news was being spread regarding the spread of the virus and even vaccine usage.

17. Conclusion

We live in the era of digitisation and technology. Social media platforms have become an integral part of everybody's life. Even if we try to reduce our presence in the virtual world, we will still use some of the other application for any of our work. Several such platforms such as LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter etc. which are being most commonly used by people across the globe.

Every coin has two sides, and so does social media. While the one hand, it has helped us make sure that the information reaches a large number of people, it proves easy access to information. On the other hand, it has also led to severe problems like addiction to the internet, depression, sleeping disorders and the spread of fake news. Thus, it becomes essential for us to always keep the positives and advantages of social media that we receive more than the negatives consequences that we have to face. The two case studies cited in the chapter helped us understand both the positives and negative impacts of social media.

Similarly, even in the current COVID-19 pandemic, social media has been a lot helpful in disseminating valuable information to a large number of people, conducting virtual classes and facilitating work from home. But it has also led to the spread of some misinformation and rumours.

Thus, social media has impacted the lives of everybody. Whether we accept it or not, today is surrounded by social media platforms and uses it in some form or the other. In this technology-savvy era, we have become dependent on digital sites, just beginning the new normal.

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